

PROTOCOL FOR MITIGATION INTERVENTIONS EVALUATION IN KENYA, SOUTH AFRICA, AND ZIMBABWE

Deliverable 5.7

PROTOCOL FOR MITIGATION INTERVENTIONS EVALUATION IN KENYA, SOUTH AFRICA, AND ZIMBABWE

HIGH HORIZONS – D5.7

[GRANT NO. 101057843]

Deliverable Information	
Title	Protocol for mitigation interventions evaluation in Kenya, South Africa and Zimbabwe: The use of the Aga Khan Development Network Carbon Management Tool to evaluate climate mitigation interventions in health facilities in Kenya, South Africa, and Zimbabwe
Deliverable number	D5.7
WP number	WP5
Author(s)	Kenya (AKHS) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sohail Muhammad Syed, Principal Investigator ▪ Aquinius Mung'atia, Co-Investigator South Africa (Wits RHI) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Gloria Maimela, Principal Investigator ▪ Craig Parker, Co-Investigator ▪ Matthew Chersich, Principal Investigator Zimbabwe (CeSHHAR) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Stanley Luchters, Principal Investigator ▪ Thabani Muronzie, Co-Investigator ▪ Jetina Tsvaki, Co-Investigator LSHTM <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Giulia Greco, Co-Investigator ▪ Josephine Borgi, Co-investigator
Lead beneficiary	CeSHHAR
Type	R – Document, Report
Dissemination Level	PU – Public
Due date	31 December 2022; extended to 31 March 2023

History of Changes	
Version 0.1	Draft created by Beneficiary CeSHHAR (1 November 2022)
Version 0.2	Suggestions from partners integrated (28 February 2023)
Version 1.0	Final version approved by all Beneficiaries (13 March 2023)
Version 1.1	Minor changes to ensure approval by all Beneficiaries (24 April 2023)

This document is issued within the frame and for the purpose of the HIGH Horizons project. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Framework Programme under Grant Agreement number 101057843. Project partner LSHTM is funded by UKRI Innovate UK reference number 10038478. The opinions expressed and arguments employed herein do not necessarily reflect the official views of the European Commission or UKRI. The dissemination of this document reflects only the author's view, and the European Commission and UKRI are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. This deliverable is subject to final acceptance by the European Commission. This document and its content are the property of the HIGH Horizons Consortium. The content of all or parts of this document can be used and distributed provided that the HIGH Horizons project and the document are properly referenced. Each HIGH Horizons Partner may use this document in conformity with the HIGH Horizons Consortium Grant Agreement provisions.

Table of Contents

- Investigators 6
- Partners in the project 7
- Protocol synopsis 8
- Definitions 9
- 1 Introduction and background..... 11
 - 1.1 The overall HIGH Horizons project 11
 - 1.2 Problem statement/rationale 12
 - 1.3 The focus of this protocol 13
- 2 Study sites..... 14
 - 2.1 Kenyan sites description 14
 - 2.2 South African sites description 14
 - 2.3 Zimbabwean sites description 16
- 3 Study design 21
 - 3.1 Methodology 21
 - 3.2 Carbon emission measurement 22
 - 3.3 Optimization modelling of mitigation interventions in health facilities.. 28
 - 3.4 Implementation of mitigation interventions in health facilities 29
 - 3.5 Effectiveness and cost of mitigation interventions in health facilities 30
 - 3.6 Roles and responsibilities 30
- 4 Study procedures..... 32
- 5 Data management and analysis 32
 - 5.1 Data management..... 32
 - 5.2 Data analysis 34
 - 5.3 Cost-effectiveness analysis..... 35

6	Quality Assurance	37
7	Ethics and dissemination	38
7.1	Research ethics approval.....	38
7.2	Dissemination	41
7.3	Strengths	43
7.4	Limitations.....	44
8	References	45
9	Annexure A	50
9.1	Kenya schedule of activities	50
9.2	South Africa schedule of activities	51
9.3	Zimbabwe schedule of activities	52

List of tables

Table 1: Definitions used in this protocol.	9
Table 2: Climatic, socio-economic, and maternal and newborn health characteristics of the study sites.	20
Table 3: Defining scopes of the AKDN tool.	22
Table 4: Sources of greenhouse gas emissions in healthcare facilities.	24
Table 5: Variables of interest.....	26
Table 6: Study procedure.....	32
Table 7: Cost-effectiveness analysis of carbon mitigation interventions in healthcare facilities.	37

List of figures

Figure 1: Maps of the location of the hospital and CHCs in South Africa.	15
Figure 2: Zimbabwe study sites.....	17
Figure 3: Mt Darwin District Hospital.	18
Figure 4: Dotito Rural Health Care Clinic.....	19
Figure 5: Chitse Rural Health Care Clinic.....	19
Figure 6: AKDN tool cover page.	23

Investigators

This task within the HIGH Horizons project is led by a team of investigators from Kenya (AKHS), United Kingdom (LSTHM), South Africa (Wits RHI), and Zimbabwe (CeSHHAR).

In Kenya, the team is led by Sohail Muhammad Syed, the Chief Executive Officer of Aga Khan Hospital Mombasa Cluster, and Aquinius Mung'atia, the Head of Projects and Security at Aga Khan Hospital Mombasa.

LSHTM team brings recognised experience in health economics and evaluation of interventions.

In South Africa, the Wits RHI team consists of Gloria Maimela, the Climate and Health Director, Matthew Chersich, a Research Professor and Craig Parker, a Data Scientist.

In Zimbabwe, the Centre for Sexual Health and HIV/AIDS Research team consists of Stanley Luchters, Professor and Executive Director, Thabani Muronzie, Climate & Health Research Officer and Jetina Tsvaki, Climate & Health Data Scientist and Management Officer.

The core project team brings a wealth of experience and expertise in climate and health research, health economics, data science, and management to this project.

Partners in the project

Partners implementing the mitigation interventions:

- 1) *Aga Khan Health Sciences Kenya (AKHS)* - brings expertise in modelling carbon emissions from facilities and implementing selected interventions.
- 2) *Centre for Sexual Health and HIV/AIDS Research Zimbabwe (CeSHHAR)* - specializes in maternal, neonatal, and child health research, community-based intervention research, and anthropology.
- 3) *London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine (LSHTM)* - has recognised expertise in maternal and child health epidemiology, health systems and in health economics.
- 4) *Wits RHI, University of the Witwatersrand, South Africa* - provides expertise in climate change and health, statistics, maternal health, anthropology, and intervention co-creation.

Protocol synopsis

Background: Climate change is a major threat to global health, and its impact on health in Sub-Saharan Africa is not well understood, which makes it difficult to assess health risks and formulate effective policies. The healthcare sector significantly contributes to carbon emissions and reducing its carbon footprint is essential for mitigating climate change. To address this issue, a phased approach will be taken to use the Aga Khan Development Network's (AKDN) Carbon Management Tool to assess the carbon footprint of eight healthcare facilities in Kenya (n=2), South Africa (n=3), and Zimbabwe (n=3).

Methods: The study will use a three-phased approach to measure the carbon footprint of each facility using the AKDN tool, develop a resource allocation tool for mitigation strategies, and evaluate the success of mitigation strategies in reducing greenhouse gas emissions and their cost-effectiveness. The goal is to provide valuable insights for future sustainability efforts of the health system.

Study outputs: The study's results will provide critical information on greenhouse gas emissions in health facilities and guide policy decisions around the interface between adaptation and especially mitigation. By using a phased approach, the study will provide a comprehensive assessment of the carbon footprint of healthcare facilities in three sub-Saharan African countries.

Conclusion: The AKDN Carbon Management Tool will enable the assessment of the carbon footprint of selected healthcare facilities in three sub-Saharan African countries. This information is crucial for developing effective policies and implementing interventions to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and mitigate climate change's impact on health. The study's results will guide policy decisions around mitigation interventions, with the allocative efficiency tool aiding in allocating resources in a way that maximizes emission reductions and health outcomes for a given level of resources.

Definitions

Table 1: Definitions used in this protocol.

Term	Definition
Adaptation	Adjusting to the impacts of climate change to minimize harm and take advantage of potential opportunities
Anaesthetic gases	Gases used in medical procedures to induce anaesthesia, which can be potent greenhouse gases
Carbon footprint	The total amount of greenhouse gas emissions produced by an organization or facility
Carbon read-outs	Measurements of carbon emissions or carbon footprints
CO ₂ equivalent	A metric measurement used to compare emissions from various greenhouse gases to an equivalent of carbon
Communication and dissemination strategy	A plan for communicating and disseminating information to stakeholders in an effective and targeted manner
Cost-benefit analysis	A type of economic evaluation where the costs and benefits of an intervention and its alternative are expressed in monetary units.
Cost-effectiveness analysis	A type of economic evaluation where the costs of an intervention and its alternative are expressed in monetary units and the benefits are expressed in natural units.
Direct emissions	Greenhouse gas emissions that result directly from an organization's activities or operations
Early Warning System	A system that uses indicators to identify potential hazards and provide advanced warning to those who may be affected
Embodied carbon	The total carbon emissions produced during the life cycle of a product or material, including production, transportation, and disposal
Emissions	The release of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere. Emissions can be direct, such as from burning fossil fuels, or indirect, such as from the production of electricity used to power a building or process. Emissions are typically measured in tons of CO ₂ equivalent (tCO ₂ e)
Emissions scopes	The different categories of emissions that are accounted for in a carbon footprint assessment
Emissions hotspots	Areas or processes within an organization that produce a disproportionately high amount of greenhouse gas emissions
Greenhouse gas emissions	Gases that trap heat in the atmosphere and contribute to global warming, including carbon dioxide, methane, and nitrous oxide
Greenhouse gases (GHGs)	Any of the gases that contribute to the greenhouse effect, including carbon dioxide (CO ₂), methane (CH ₄), nitrous oxide (N ₂ O), fluorinated gases, and others
Indirect emissions	Greenhouse gas emissions that result from activities or operations that support an organization, such as energy consumption or waste disposal
Indirect impacts	Effects of climate change that occur as a result of other impacts, such as changes in infectious disease patterns due to shifting mosquito populations
Intervention mapping	A methodology for designing and implementing interventions that involve collaboration with stakeholders at each step

Term	Definition
Longitudinal measurement design	A study design that involves measuring a variable over time to identify trends or changes
Mitigation interventions	Actions taken to reduce or offset the carbon emissions of a facility or organization
Mitigation strategies	Actions taken to reduce or prevent the negative impacts of climate change
Multi-faceted approach	A method that involves multiple strategies or approaches to address a problem
Optimization modelling	The process of using mathematical models to find the most efficient solution to a problem
Pre-industrial level	The global temperature level before the Industrial Revolution (approximately mid-19th century)
Predictive modelling	Using data and statistical methods to make predictions about future events or outcomes
Refrigerant gases	Gases used in refrigeration and air conditioning systems, which can contribute to emissions through leaks or improper disposal
Spend mapping	The process of tracking and analysing financial spending within an organization or facility
Supply chain	The network of companies and suppliers involved in the production, transportation, and delivery of goods and services and the associated information flows. A sustainable supply chain consists of the consideration of environmental, social, and economic impacts throughout the supply chain, from the sourcing of raw materials to the disposal of products at the end of their life cycle
Temperature anomaly	The difference between the current global average temperature and the pre-industrial level
Vulnerability	The degree to which one is able to be easily hurt, influenced or attacked

1 Introduction and background

Over the past decades, the world has witnessed a rising trend in extreme weather events, such as heatwaves, droughts, and hurricanes, which are linked to the accelerating pace of climate change [1]. The effects of these extreme weather events are far-reaching and impact various aspects of life, including human health [2]. Pregnant women, infants, and health workers are among the most affected by climate change in low-resource settings, as they are particularly susceptible to the negative impacts of extreme heat [3]. The health impacts of climate change are diverse and complex, including but not limited to heat exhaustion, dehydration, cardiovascular disease, respiratory distress, and mental health issues [4].

Furthermore, the effects of climate change are not limited to the direct impacts of extreme weather events. Indirect impacts, such as the spread of infectious diseases due to increased and shifting mosquito populations, air pollution, and food and water insecurity, pose additional threats to human health [5]. These health impacts are of significant concern in low- and middle-income countries, where most of the global population resides, as these countries are often ill-equipped to address and mitigate the negative impacts of climate change [6].

1.1 The overall HIGH Horizons project

In response to these growing concerns, the HIGH Horizons project was developed to address knowledge gaps in the surveillance and tracking of the impacts of climate change on health. The project involves six partners in Europe, three in Africa, and one international organization. It focuses on pregnant and postpartum women, infants, and health workers as the primary groups affected by climate change. Through the implementation of a personalised Early Warning System (EWS) and integrated adaptation-mitigation actions in health facilities, the project

aims to quantify and monitor direct and indirect health impacts of extreme heat and communicate findings to relevant stakeholders to inform policy decisions.

Other collaborating partners in the HIGH Horizons consortium:

- 1) *Ghent University (UGENT)* - serves as the overall project coordinator.
- 2) *Karolinska Institutet (KI)* - brings expertise in maternal and perinatal health epidemiology and clinical knowledge in antenatal care practices.
- 3) *Lunds Universitet (ULUND)* and *Danmarks Tekniske Universitet (DTU)* - offer unique technologies for Early Warning Systems (EWS) and critical capacity in coding for tailoring the ClimApp to the target audience and optimizing its functionality.
- 4) *University of Graz (UNI GRAZ)* - provides support in societal impacts of climate change, social vulnerability, and inequality analysis.
- 5) *World Health Organization (WHO)* - provides guidance on indicators and surveillance and ensures the project findings are adequately exploited at the EU and global level.

1.2 Problem statement/rationale

Climate change poses a significant threat to human health, as rising temperatures can lead to an increased risk of heat-related illnesses and diseases. To develop effective climate policy, it's important to quantify and monitor the impacts of heat, evaluate the costs and benefits of different interventions, and prioritize resources to protect those who may be most affected [2].

Healthcare facilities significantly contribute to greenhouse gas emissions due to their energy-intensive operations, which include heating, cooling, lighting, ventilation, medical equipment, and waste management [32]. While reducing these emissions has the potential for direct health benefits, there is a lack of evidence regarding the cost-effectiveness of mitigation strategies implemented in healthcare facilities [33].

The HIGH Horizons project aligns with the Paris Agreement under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, which aims to limit global warming and protect against the impacts of climate change [34].

1.3 The focus of this protocol

This protocol outlines the approach and tools for assessing and evaluating carbon emissions from health facilities, namely Kenya, South Africa, and Zimbabwe which form one component of the overall HIGH Horizons project. This component of the HIGH Horizons project does not directly focus on maternal and child health outcomes. The primary objectives of this component include utilizing the Aga Khan Development Network's (AKDN) Carbon Management Tool [7] to assess carbon emissions generated by health facilities (Objective 1), developing a resource allocation tool for mitigation strategies, and implement mitigation strategies to decrease greenhouse gas emissions in health facilities (Objective 2), evaluating the mitigation strategies in terms of their cost-effectiveness and reduction in greenhouse gas emissions (Objective 3), and communicating and disseminating the findings to relevant stakeholders through the design and implementation of an effective communication and dissemination strategy (Objective 4) [8]. The goal is to learn lessons about reducing carbon emissions from the healthcare sector. This project's component will provide valuable insights for future sustainability efforts and track progress over time through serial measurements.

The study outputs will be crucial to furthering our understanding of the impacts of climate change on health and informing policy and practice aimed at improving human health. This includes but is not limited to populations such as low-income communities, indigenous peoples, elderly individuals, pregnant women, children, and those with pre-existing health conditions. These populations may be at higher risk for the negative health impacts of climate change. Thus, efforts to reduce

carbon emissions and mitigate these impacts are particularly important for their well-being [9].

2 Study sites

2.1 Kenyan sites description

❖ **Aga Khan Hospital, Mombasa and Aga Khan Medical Centre-Kilifi**

The study will take place in two healthcare facilities in Kenya: the Aga Khan Hospital in Mombasa, which serves as the Secondary Care Field Site, and the Aga Khan Medical Centre in Kilifi, the Primary Field Site. The regions of Mombasa and Kilifi have a tropical climate, with temperatures ranging from 21°C to 32°C and average annual rainfall ranging from 300mm to 1200mm [10]. These areas experience seasonal changes in precipitation and temperatures, which could affect the spread of infectious diseases [11]. Both sites offer maternal, newborn, and child health (MNCH) services staffed by qualified personnel, including obstetrician-gynaecologists, midwives, ward and outpatient nurses, and paediatrician consultants. The patient volume at the sites for the past six months has been steady, with an average of 50 daily visits to the outpatient department and 600 admissions per month.

2.2 South African sites description

The study will be conducted in an urban setting characterized by a subtropical climate with dry winters and hot summers: in Tshwane, located near Johannesburg in Gauteng Province [12]. The region has experienced an increased frequency and intensity of extreme weather events such as heatwaves, droughts, and heavy rainfall due to climate change [13]. The closest TAHMO weather station is TA00244 Midrand Fire Station, Cedar Road, Broadacres, with an average annual rainfall total of 657 mm [14]. The World Bank Income group (GDP per capita) for

Tshwane is an upper-middle income group of \$6,994 [15]. Three maternity facilities in the study area offer various healthcare services, including emergency care, maternal and child health, treatment for acute and chronic diseases, and primary health services such as dental and reproductive health, mental health, and social services. Pregnant women residing in Urban Heat Islands, where concrete and steel structures absorb and retain heat, have limited means of reducing heat exposure during a heatwave, and health facilities, poorly built brick dwellings and informal housing in urban slums offer little to no protection against heat exposure [4].

Figure 1: Maps of the location of the hospital and CHCs in South Africa.

❖ **Laudium Community Health Centre**

The Laudium Community Health Centre (CHC) is located in Pretoria West and serves a population of approximately 245,387 individuals [16]. The facility offers a comprehensive array of health services, including emergency care, maternal and child health, treatment for acute, chronic, and non-communicable diseases, primary health services such as dental care, reproductive health, mental health,

and social services, as well as rehabilitation services such as audiology, speech, and hearing [17].

❖ **Stanza Bopape Community Health Centre**

The Mamelodi District Hospital and Stanza Bopape Community Health Centre are in Region 4, East of Tshwane, which covers an area of 49.19 km² [18]. Stanza Bopape CHC serves a population of 261,989 and offers essential healthcare services such as peer counselling, a crisis centre for gender-based violence and sexual assault victims, antiretroviral therapy adherence clubs, COVID-19 screening, and home delivery of medication [17].

❖ **Mamelodi District Hospital**

Mamelodi District Hospital is a referral centre for patients needing higher-level care, including pregnant women with obstetric emergencies. The hospital has a catchment population of 334,577. It offers clinical specialties in medicine, surgery, obstetrics, paediatrics, psychiatry, radiology, emergency medical services, trauma, and clinical management of NCDs, HIV/AIDS, and TB [17, 19].

2.3 Zimbabwean sites description

The study will be conducted in a rural setting characterized by a humid subtropical climate with dry winters and hot summers: Mount Darwin District, located in Mashonaland Central Province [20, 21]. The average annual highest temperature is 33.3°C (91.9°F) [20], and the yearly temperature is 24.59°C (76.26°F) [22] and is 1.86% higher than Zimbabwe's averages. Mount Darwin typically receives about 126.12 mm of precipitation annually, and the area is projected to become drier over time [22]. The World Bank Income group (GDP per capita) for Mount Darwin is a lower-middle income group of \$1,737 [23].

Figure 2: Zimbabwe study sites.

The selected public health facilities in the study area provide primary care and referral services, including antenatal care, outpatient and inpatient services, and maternity care. The population in the district relies mainly on farming, artisanal gold mining and some informal economic activities. The district population stands at approximately 240 727 [24] people . The maternal mortality ratio per 100,000 live births is high, with 462 maternal deaths recorded, and the lifetime risk of maternal death is 1 in 53 [25, 26].

❖ Mt Darwin District Hospital

Mt Darwin District hospital serves as a primary care and referral health facility for the district. The facility services include curative, preventative, maternity, postnatal, inpatient, outpatient, male and female wards, theatre, laboratory, and pharmacy [28]. The average number of women attending antenatal visits in the first month is 80, and the average number of deliveries per year is 2000 [29].

Figure 3: Mt Darwin District Hospital.

❖ Dotito Rural Health Care Clinic

Dotito Rural Health Care Clinic is a primary care clinic situated 28 kilometres from Mt. Darwin District Hospital [30]. It offers services that include curative (chronic condition screening, monitoring and follow-up, TB screening, initiation, and management), maternity-related services (antenatal care, booking follow-up visit, delivery), postnatal care (visual inspection with acetic acid and cervicography for cancer) as well as outpatient and inpatient related services. On a monthly average, the hospital provides services to 80 patients in the outpatient department. The maternity ward has a monthly average of 25-30 deliveries and a yearly average of 292 deliveries [29].

Figure 4: Dotito Rural Health Care Clinic.

❖ Chitse Rural Health Care Clinic

Chitse Rural Health Care Clinic is situated 18 km from Mt. Darwin Hospital [31]. The clinic offers similar services as Dotito Rural Health Care. Services offered include curative, maternity-related services, postnatal care, outpatient and inpatient-related services. On average 18-20 monthly deliveries and about 230 deliveries yearly are recorded [29].

Figure 5: Chitse Rural Health Care Clinic.

Table 2: Climatic, socio-economic, and maternal and newborn health characteristics of the study sites.

Variable	Tshwane, Gauteng Province, South Africa	Mount Darwin District, Mashonaland Central Province, Zimbabwe	Aga Khan Hospital in Mombasa (Secondary Care Field Site), Aga Khan Medical Centre in Kilifi (Primary Field Site), Kenya
Average daily maximum temperature (°C)	28.8 (January)	32.3 (October)	30.3 (February)
Average daily temperature of warmest month (°C)	22.8 (January)	25.6 (November)	27.5 (March)
Average annual rainfall total (mm)	657	730	700
Days with max apparent temp ≥ 32 °C [5]	38	92	40
Climate zone (Köppen-Geiger classification)	Subtropical (Cwb)	Humid subtropical (Cwb)	Tropical (Am)
Health facilities	Laudium Community Health Centre, Mamelodi District Hospital, Stanza Bopape Community Health Centre	Mt Darwin District Hospital, Chitse Rural Health Care Clinic, Dotito Rural Health Care Clinic	Aga Khan Medical Centre in Kilifi (primary field site), Aga Khan Hospital in Mombasa (secondary care field site)
Maternal mortality ratio per 100,000 live births (country level)	155.9 [8]	462 [9]	342 [18]
Lifetime risk of maternal death (country level)	1 in 330 [10]	1 in 53 [9]	1 in 69 [19]
Number of new women attending antenatal clinic in study area per month	268 [11]	235 [12]	500 [20]
Number of maternity facilities in study area	3	3	2
Predominant housing type	Informal housing with tin sheeting and low-cost government housing	Brick housing, or mud and pole	Brick and mud houses, modern houses
Birth in a health facility	97.3% [13]	93% [14]	70% [21]
Preterm birth rate	12.6% [15]	17% [12]	12.5% [22]
Low birth weight rate	13% [16]	8.8% [9]	10.2% [22]
Stillbirth rate per 1000 live births	18 [13]	13 [12]	21.5 [23]
Caesarean section rate	26.0% [16]	4% [14]	9.3% [22]
Neonatal mortality rate per 1000 live births	12.2 [17]	33 [12]	17.8 [23]

3 Study design

3.1 Methodology

The study will be guided by a methodological framework consisting of three phases. In the first phase, the carbon footprint of each health facility will be measured using the AKDN Carbon Management Tool. This phase aims to establish a baseline measurement of carbon emissions for each facility, which will serve as a reference point for subsequent evaluations.

In the second phase, a resource allocation tool for mitigation strategies will be developed, and mitigation strategies will be implemented to decrease greenhouse gas emissions in health facilities. The specific steps involved in this phase will be unpacked in the subsequent sections of the document. It is important to note that this phase will be carried out by research staff from the partners within the HIGH Horizons project and discussed with stakeholders at health facilities in each country.

The final phase of the study will involve the evaluation of the mitigation strategies in reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and cost-effectiveness. Again, the specific steps involved in this phase will be elaborated in the subsequent sections of the document.

Overall, the study will employ a rigorous methodology that involves careful measurement, analysis, and evaluation of the impact of mitigation interventions in health facilities. Each phase of the study will be detailed in the subsequent sections of the report, with a clear description of the activities involved, the steps taken, and the responsible parties.

3.2 Carbon emission measurement

A serial, longitudinal measurement design will be employed to assess the carbon emissions of health facilities in Kenya, South Africa and Zimbabwe. This approach involves measuring carbon emissions at monthly intervals using the AKDN Carbon Management Tool, an integrated Excel-based system designed for measuring and analysing carbon emissions [7]. The tool covers three scopes, Scope 1, 2, and 3, which enable a comprehensive evaluation of greenhouse gas emissions, including those from supply chains (see table 3). The tool can handle specific emissions from the health sector, such as anaesthetic gases, respiratory inhalers, and emissions from energy, transport, waste, and refrigerants. The tool automatically calculates carbon footprints and assigns emissions scopes, providing instant carbon read-outs and diagnostic dashboards that can be used to identify emissions hotspots. This methodology is deemed the most appropriate for trend analysis and will provide valuable information on the effectiveness of mitigation measures over time.

Table 3: Defining scopes of the AKDN tool.

Emissions scope	Definition	Example
Scope 1	Direct emissions from the organization's activity	Burning fuel or waste on the premises, using anaesthetic gases, emissions from company vehicles
Scope 2	Indirect emissions from energy consumed by the organization	Buying and consuming electricity, steam, heat, or cooling from local authorities, emissions from purchased fuels, such as natural gas for heating
Scope 3	Indirect emissions from products or services used to support the organization's operations	Purchased goods and services, waste disposal, employee commuting, business travel, investments, leased assets, transportation of goods and services

Figure 6: AKDN tool cover page.

AKDN Carbon Management Tool		Additional support on how to use the tool can be found in the associated guide	The AKDN Carbon Mangement Tool is continually being improved and updated with feedback from its users. For guidance on its use, to share feedback and to access future updates please contact:	healthcarbonfootprint@akdn.org							
		All users must commit to acknowledging AKDN and the use of this tool wherever results are shared or published									
Headings and guidance are marked grey		Step 1	Complete all pink cells on this 'Cover Sheet'. The selecting the appropriate country on this sheet is required to ensure that the carbon calculations on later sheets accurately reflect country specific variables. Only report data for one country and one agency/organisation per workbook.								
Input cells are marked pink <i>(Input cells essential for calculations are in dark pink)</i>		Step 2	Complete all pink cells on the 'Buildings' sheet, maximum of 30 buildings per workbook. Input the names of all buildings/sites or groups of sites to be reported. Entering floor area data here enables carbon intensity benchmarks to be populated on the 'Building Totals & benchmarking sheet'								
Output cells are marked in green		Step 3	Complete the rest of the pink cells on all other sheets as you have data for. The power use sheets cover energy, water, anaesthetic gases, refrigerants, waste, water, inhalers, contractor logistics and construction. You may not need to complete every sheet. Use the 'Narrative' box at the top of each sheet to explain any significant changes since the last report. Inputting your organisations spending data on the Procurement sheets will enable you to estimate the carbon emissions in your supply chain. With this you can identify carbon hotspots and priority suppliers to engage. To avoid common errors: 1. Avoid copying and pasting data or text into the sheets. If you do, paste as 'values only'. 2. When drop down menus are available they must be used 3. Do not change the names entered for buildings once you have started to complete the sheets.								
		Step 4	Complete/update relevant pink cells on the 'Actions Tracker' sheet to highlight key actions that are currently underway or planned.								
Details of reporting organisation											
Agency/Organisation name:											
Country:		Algeria	Note: Only report data for one country per workbook								
Region (in country):											
Reporting Period (months):		Start:				End:					
Date Prepared:											
Name of person preparing report:											
Phone number:											
		Cover Sheet	Changes since last version	\$ Conversion	Totals	Supply Chain Totals	Buildi ...	+	:	←	

❖ Sources of emissions specific to the healthcare facility

Table 4 provides an overview of the sources specific to healthcare facilities that can contribute to carbon emissions. The table highlights the various sources of emissions that can result from energy consumption within healthcare facilities, vehicle use, travel distances, and the use of certain medical equipment, such as anaesthetic gases and respiratory inhalers. Additionally, the table also covers emissions resulting from refrigerant gases used in air conditioning and refrigeration systems, water usage, waste disposal, and the travel of vehicles other than those owned by healthcare facilities, such as patient or visitor vehicles. By understanding the sources of emissions, healthcare facilities can identify areas where they can implement strategies to reduce their carbon footprint and improve their sustainability.

Table 4: Sources of greenhouse gas emissions in healthcare facilities.

Sources of emissions	Description
Energy	Energy consumption within healthcare facilities can contribute to emissions from electricity and heating and other sources such as natural gas, propane, and fuel oil
Vehicle Fuel	Using vehicles for healthcare facilities, such as ambulances, delivery vehicles, and staff vehicles can contribute to emissions
Vehicle Distance	The distance vehicles travel to and from healthcare facilities can also contribute to emissions
Travel Other Vehicles	Emissions from travel by vehicles other than those owned by healthcare facilities, such as patient or visitor vehicles, may also contribute to the overall carbon footprint
Anaesthetic Gases	Anaesthetic gases used in medical procedures are potent greenhouse gases and their use in healthcare facilities can contribute to emissions
Refrigerant Gases	Refrigerants used in air conditioning systems, refrigerators, and freezers can also contribute to emissions through leaks or improper disposal
Water	Water usage in healthcare facilities can result in emissions through the energy used in treatment, pumping, and heating processes
Waste	Disposing of waste from healthcare facilities can result in emissions from landfills and waste-to-energy processes
Inhalers	Respiratory inhalers in healthcare facilities can also contribute to emissions by producing and disposing of these products

❖ Supply chain contribution to carbon emissions in health facilities

Healthcare facilities can contribute to carbon emissions through various processes, including construction and maintenance, procurement of goods and services, and waste disposal. By implementing sustainable practices, healthcare facilities can reduce their carbon footprint and improve their sustainability. This section provides an overview of the various aspects of healthcare facility management that can contribute to carbon emissions and highlights strategies to reduce emissions. These include selecting materials with low embodied carbon, implementing sustainable procurement policies, and analysing financial spending to identify areas where emissions can be reduced. By understanding the sources of emissions and their impact on the facility's carbon footprint, healthcare facilities can prioritize investments in low-carbon goods and services and improve their carbon management. These categories are part of the categories recorded in the supply chain management sheets of the AKDN tool.

- *Construction Materials*: The materials used in the construction and maintenance of healthcare facilities can contribute to emissions through the production and transportation of these materials. Choosing materials with low embodied carbon, such as sustainably sourced wood or recycled materials, can help to reduce emissions [7].
- *Contractor Logistics*: The transportation and disposal of waste generated by contractors working in healthcare facilities can also contribute to emissions. Implementing sustainable procurement policies and practices, such as requiring contractors to reduce emissions and waste, can help to reduce emissions [7].
- *Procurement_T2*: T2 procurement refers to the procurement of goods and services for the day-to-day operations of healthcare facilities. Selecting products and services with low emissions, such as energy-efficient equipment or green cleaning products, can help to reduce emissions [7].
- *Procurement_T3*: T3 procurement refers to procuring goods and services for capital projects, such as construction or renovation. Choosing materials and equipment with low embodied carbon and implementing sustainable procurement practices, such as considering product lifecycle impacts, can help reduce emissions [7].
- *Spend Mapping*: Spend mapping tracks and analyses financial spending within healthcare facilities. This information can be used to identify areas where emissions can be reduced and to prioritize investments in low-carbon goods and services.

❖ **Action tracker sheet and four data output sheets**

The tool calculates the carbon footprint for all data provided and automatically assigns emissions scopes. It converts input data into instant carbon read-outs and diagnostic dashboards. Emissions outputs appear on each line, and totals appear

at the top of each sheet as a sheet is completed. Four separate sheets (Error checking, Totals, Supply Chain Totals, Building Totals & Benchmarking) provide dashboards and charts to help consolidate and interrogate the data. These include a high-level summary and per m² facility benchmarking to help identify hotspots at a facility and at an organization level. The tool output is a set of facility-specific potential mitigation target points weighed against emissions modelling and cost-benefits [7].

❖ **Variables of interest**

To better understand how carbon emissions are calculated in healthcare facilities, it is essential to look at the variables of interest that feed into the calculation. Table 5 provides an overview of the variables that will be collected and converted into CO₂ emissions, such as building ownership, floor area, energy consumption, fuel consumption, vehicle distance, and waste generation. Additionally, details of procurement, construction materials, and logistics for contractors will be recorded, as well as progress made over time on initiatives to reduce carbon footprint. The table also includes a currency conversion rate, which will be used to convert local currency to a common currency for data analysis. By capturing these variables, healthcare facilities can better understand their carbon footprint and implement strategies to reduce emissions.

Table 5: Variables of interest.

Sheet name	Variables collected	Details of measures
Buildings	Name, Ownership ² , Floor Area	Information about the building's name, ownership (whether it is owned or rented), and the floor area in square meters
Energy	Details of energy consumption	Details of electricity, gas, and steam consumption for heating, cooling, and other purposes, in kWh or G.J.
Vehicle Fuel	Details of fuel consumption	Details of fuel consumption for vehicles, in litres or gallons
Vehicle Distance	Details of vehicle distance	Details of the distance travelled by vehicles, in kilometres or miles. This will be useful where there is missing data on "vehicle fuel"

Sheet name	Variables collected	Details of measures
Travel Other Vehicles	Details of other vehicle travel	Details of the distance travelled by other modes of transportation, such as trains or airplanes, in kilometres or miles
Anaesthetic Gases	Details of anaesthetic gas usage	Details of the quantity and type of anaesthetic gases used, in litres or pounds
Refrigerant Gases	Details of refrigerant gas usage	Details of the quantity and type of refrigerant gases used, in kilograms or pounds
Water	Details of water usage	Details of water consumption for domestic, industrial, and medical purposes, in litres or gallons
Waste	Details of waste generation	Details of the type and quantity of waste generated, in kilograms or pounds
Inhalers	Details of inhaler usage	Details of the number and type of inhalers used
Construction Materials	Details of construction materials used	Details of the quantity and type of construction materials used, in kilograms or pounds
Contractor Logistics	Details of contractor logistics	Details of transportation and logistics activities for contractors, in kilometres or miles
Procurement_T2	Details of procurement	Details of procurement for equipment, appliances, and other materials, in dollars or local currency
Procurement_T3	Details of procurement	Details of procurement for services, in dollars or local currency
Spend Mapping	Details of expenditures	Details of expenditures for all categories, including salaries, benefits, and other expenses, in dollars or local currency
Action Tracker	Progress made over time on initiatives to reduce carbon footprint	Details of the initiatives taken to reduce carbon emissions, such as implementing renewable energy sources, energy efficiency measures, and waste reduction
Currency Conversion Rate	Currency conversion rate	The exchange rate used to convert local currency to a common currency for data analysis

❖ Data Quality Scores

The data collection process involves gathering information on the type and quantity of resources used. To ensure accuracy, a data quality score can be assigned for each line item. The data source is selected from a drop-down list, such as 'from supplier's bills' or 'estimates', which contributes to an overall data quality score. This score considers the number of resources used and the level of quality assigned for each line item. It is displayed below the total carbon emissions figure on each sheet.

In addition, users can input the unit cost of resources, which will be helpful when prioritizing and justifying investments in carbon reduction strategies. The carbon emissions calculated for each line item, including the carbon factor used, the emissions produced, and the scope, are located on the left-hand side of each sheet. Emissions hotspots are identified through a colour ranking system, with Red indicating the highest emissions and Green the lowest.

3.3 Optimization modelling of mitigation interventions in health facilities

The selection of carbon mitigation interventions will be based on their effectiveness and cost-effectiveness [35]. To enhance the study's impact, the team plans to utilize the Atomica modelling package (67), to determine the best package of interventions tailored to address the carbon hotspots in each facility. The AKDN Carbon Management Tool will be employed to establish a baseline understanding of these hotspots and provide crucial information for the optimization model [36]. The Atomica modelling package is a powerful, flexible tool that allows users to simulate the impact of various interventions on complex systems. By analysing the interactions between interventions and their effects on the identified carbon hotspots, the Atomica package can help identify the most effective and cost-efficient combinations of interventions to be implemented in each healthcare facility.

The optimization process will be carried out in the following sequence:

1. Utilize the AKDN Carbon Management Tool to gather baseline information on carbon hotspots in each facility.
2. Organize a stakeholder workshop to gather input and feedback from relevant stakeholders in the healthcare sector.

3. Combine stakeholder input with data from the AKDN Carbon Management Tool to refine the Atomica optimization model, ensuring the proposed mitigation interventions effectively address the identified carbon hotspots.
4. Implement the selected interventions based on the optimization model in each facility.
5. Assess the effectiveness and cost-effectiveness of the implemented interventions to provide valuable insights for future iterations of the optimization model and guide the implementation of carbon mitigation interventions in other healthcare facilities.

By following this sequence, the HIGH Horizons project aims to develop and implement the most effective and cost-efficient carbon mitigation interventions to reduce the carbon footprint of healthcare facilities.

3.4 Implementation of mitigation interventions in health facilities

The project is implementing a range of interventions to reduce carbon emissions in MNCH facilities in Kenya, South Africa and Zimbabwe. Once areas for intervention are identified, an action plan will be developed, outlining specific activities and timelines for implementation. The HIGH Horizons research teams in these three countries will be responsible for implementing the interventions. Progress will be monitored through serial measurements of carbon emissions, using the AKDN Carbon Management Tool.

In all sites the interventions will be customized to meet the unique needs, available financial resources and circumstances of the location. In Kenya, the mitigation interventions could include installing solar Photovoltaic (PV) systems, modifying buildings for natural ventilation and shading, and replacing air-conditioning units with more energy-efficient alternatives. In Zimbabwe, the project will possibly implement environmentally friendly waste management practices, reduce

harmful refrigerants, and plant trees for shade and carbon offset. In South Africa, the interventions might focus on reducing the use of fossil fuels, implementing waste management practices, planting trees, and replacing air-conditioning units.

3.5 Effectiveness and cost of mitigation interventions in health facilities

Phase three of this study will involve evaluating the effectiveness and cost-effectiveness of carbon mitigation interventions implemented in health facilities. The main outcome will be the reduction in tons of carbon emissions, while secondary outcomes will include additional environmental impacts (e.g., reduction in waste generation, water conservation, and energy efficiency).

To provide a comprehensive understanding of the cost and effectiveness of the interventions, we will present the results in a disaggregated format, including estimates of the mean costs with appropriate measures of dispersion associated with each intervention in a descriptive table. This will allow stakeholders, program leaders, subject experts, researchers, and decision-makers to establish context-specific relevance and relative importance [39].

Furthermore, we could explore the potential for replicability of the interventions in other health facilities or sectors [40]. This will help spread the interventions' positive impacts and contribute to a more sustainable future. Overall, primary focus is on evaluating the effectiveness of carbon mitigation interventions in health facilities by measuring their impact on the environment and human health through the primary outcome of tons of carbon emissions.

3.6 Roles and responsibilities

The success of this project's component is largely dependent on the roles and responsibilities of the research teams and the district departments of health. The

research teams will play a critical role in the implementation of each phase of the study. They will coordinate and oversee the data collection process, develop the resource allocation tool, and implement mitigation strategies to reduce greenhouse gas emissions in health facilities. Additionally, they will evaluate the success of the mitigation strategies in relation to reduction in greenhouse gas emissions and cost-effectiveness.

In phase 1, the research teams will work closely with the district department of health to measure the carbon footprint of each health facility using the AKDN Carbon Management Tool. They will also work together to collect baseline data on the energy and water use of the health facilities.

In phase 2, the research teams will develop a resource allocation tool for mitigation strategies and implement mitigation strategies to decrease greenhouse gas emissions in health facilities. This will involve working with facility staff to identify opportunities for reducing energy and water use, as well as developing and implementing a plan for reducing waste and promoting sustainable practices.

In phase 3, the research teams will evaluate the success of the mitigation strategies in terms of reduction in greenhouse gas emissions and cost-effectiveness. They will analyse the data collected in phase 1 and phase 2 to determine the effectiveness of the interventions implemented.

The district departments of health will play a critical role in facilitating access to data and providing insights into the process of implementing the study. They will also serve as a valuable partner in disseminating the findings to relevant stakeholders through a well-planned communication and dissemination strategy. However, it is important to note that the HIGH Horizons consortium is ultimately responsible for all phases of the study and will work closely with the research teams and the district departments of health to ensure the successful completion of the study.

4 Study procedures

Study procedures refer to the steps or actions taken to carry out a study successfully [41]. These procedures can include obtaining necessary approvals, collecting data, implementing interventions, evaluating outcomes, and disseminating results. The table below provides an overview of the study procedures for three countries: Kenya, South Africa and Zimbabwe. For more detailed Gantt charts please see annexure A.

Table 6: Study procedure.

Country	Procedure
Kenya	1. Utilize existing data on carbon emission monitoring, subject to approval of AKHS leadership. 2. Design and optimize a model comparing benefits and costs.
South Africa	1. Obtain approvals from relevant authorities. 2. Apply for ethics approval. 3. Conduct measurements and data collection. 4. Design and optimize a model comparing benefits and costs. 5. Implement interventions in facilities. 6. Evaluate cost-effectiveness. 7. Disseminate results through conferences, publications, and policy briefs.
Zimbabwe	1. Apply for a support letter to the Ministry of Health and Child Care. 2. Measure carbon footprints at proposed facilities. 3. Design and optimize an investment modelling tool comparing benefits and costs. 4. Implement interventions in facilities. 5. Evaluate cost-effectiveness. 6. Disseminate results through conferences, publications, and policy briefs.

5 Data management and analysis

5.1 Data management

Data management is a critical component of the HIGH Horizons research project, and the team has taken a number of measures to ensure that the collected data are secure and protected. The implementing partners in Kenya, South Africa, and Zimbabwe will be responsible for data collection and management using the AKDN Carbon Management tool V1.6.1, which is a Microsoft Excel office package. The tool will be password-protected, and access to the data will be limited to authorized team members from the respective implementing partners to prevent access by unauthorized third parties. In each country, one person in the study

team will be responsible for data management and protection project activities in compliance with relevant data protection regulations and standards, including the principle of data minimization.

To ensure the security and protection of the data, the project will follow the ISO/IEC 27001:2005 standards for data storage. The data storage will be protected against risk to prevent data loss, and the partners will take necessary measures to protect the personal data collected during the project. These measures include access controls, regular backups, and encryption. The HIGH Horizons project has a Data Management Plan (DMP) that outlines the data management life cycle and ensures data quality control (see deliverable D1.4, dd. November 2022). The DMP will be updated throughout the project to reflect the status of the project's data management activities and comply with Open Science and country regulations. The project manager at Ghent University is responsible for the overall project management and the handling of the project's SharePoint folder and files on behalf of the project.

The AKDN Carbon Management Tool will be installed on research staff laptops for data collection during facility visits in Kenya, South Africa and Zimbabwe. Once the data is entered into the tool, research staff will upload it onto a secure SharePoint server as soon as they have access to an internet connection. The data will be removed from the laptops to ensure that it is not left in any unsecured location. The SharePoint server is password-protected, and access will be granted only to authorized project team members. All data will be stored securely and the server will be regularly backed up to prevent data loss. In addition, data will be transferred using secure methods, such as encrypted file transfers, to prevent unauthorized access.

The HIGH Horizons research team takes data management and security very seriously and is committed to ensuring that all data collected during the project is

kept confidential and secure. All partners involved in the project will work together to ensure that data is managed and transferred using the latest and most secure techniques available to prevent any potential leaks. The team will continuously monitor the data management practices and take necessary measures to address any issues arising during the project. Data training on data handling and management best practices, such as data access controls, data backup and storage, and data encryption, will be conducted for researchers handling the data to ensure that they are equipped with the necessary skills and knowledge to handle and manage data securely and responsibly.

5.2 Data analysis

The totals sheet of the AKDN Carbon Management Tool is the focal point of the carbon measurement analysis, bringing together all the calculated emissions data from individual data sheets. The sheet provides an overall summary of emissions, including by source (e.g., energy, anaesthetics) and by scope (Scope 1, 2, or 3), expressed in tons of CO₂ equivalent (tCO₂e). Additionally, the sheet showcases environmental indices such as water use and renewable energy generated. At the end of each data collection period (every three months) pre and post intervention, the totals will be imported to a word document for reporting and dissemination purposes.

This analysis will vary the input parameters and evaluate their effect on the results, helping to determine the input parameters with the greatest impact and the uncertainty of the results. We will use statistical methods such as regression analysis, ANOVA, and student's t-tests to explore associations between variables. Additionally, we will use interrupted time series analysis as a technique to uncover potential relationships between interventions and reduced emissions. By varying the input parameters and evaluating their impact on the results, we can identify the input parameters with the most significant impact and uncertainty. This

analysis will help us assess the significance of relationships between variables and uncover any potential associations between interventions and reduced emissions [42].

The results of the data analysis will be presented in an easy-to-understand format using graphs, tables, and charts and will be interpreted and discussed to highlight key findings and their implications for policy and practice [43]. These findings will be disseminated through academic journals, conference presentations, and policy briefs to reach a broad audience and maximize their impact.

5.3 Cost-effectiveness analysis

The cost-effectiveness of carbon mitigation interventions in healthcare facilities will be a crucial aspect of this study. We will conduct a cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA) of different interventions to reduce carbon emissions in healthcare facilities in Kenya, South Africa and Zimbabwe. Specific requirements for a CEA include measuring the economic and financial costs of different interventions, and then comparing the cost per the same unit of outcome across the different interventions [66]. In this analysis we will take the societal perspective of both the programme and patient when assessing the costs and outcomes of the carbon reduction interventions. This means user costs will be assessed in addition to those of the provider.

To conduct the CEA, we will identify the alternative carbon reduction interventions and (1) estimate the economic and financial costs of setting up and running each alternative intervention, including start-up activities (e.g. training of staff), implementation and maintenance of intervention components; (2) combine the economic cost estimates associated with each carbon reduction intervention with their observed outcomes to calculate a cost per unit of analysis such as cost per ton of carbon reduced[55].; and (3) use observed costs and outcomes to model the cost-effectiveness of the different interventions.

The CEA will help us identify interventions that maximize carbon emission reduction benefits for healthcare facilities in the participating countries, both in the present and in the future. We will assess potential future cost savings associated with each alternative intervention, using data from the Atomica modelling package and stakeholder input. Sensitivity analysis will be conducted to test the robustness of results and to assess the impact of key parameters.

By conducting a CEA alongside carbon measurements and optimization modelling with Atomica, we will be able to compare the costs and effectiveness of different interventions and identify those that are most cost-effective. This integrated approach will provide valuable insights for decision-makers and stakeholders, ensuring that carbon mitigation interventions are both effective and economically efficient in reducing emissions within healthcare facilities.

Overall, the cost-effectiveness aspect of the research project will be critical in identifying the most economically feasible carbon reduction interventions for healthcare facilities in Kenya, South Africa and Zimbabwe. By conducting a CEA alongside the carbon measurements, we will be able to compare the costs and effectiveness of different interventions and identify those that are most cost-effective. To ensure the reliability and accuracy of our CEA, we will adhere to best practices for conducting cost-effectiveness analyses, such as using a common outcome metric and accounting for uncertainty through sensitivity analyses. By doing so, we will generate valuable information to help inform policy decisions in the participating countries and beyond (see table 7) [46].

Table 7: Cost-effectiveness analysis of carbon mitigation interventions in healthcare facilities.

Variable	Description
Primary Unit of Analysis	Tons of CO ₂ emissions from each healthcare facility
Analysis Method	Cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA) conducted concurrently with carbon measurements
Purpose	To determine the efficiency of different interventions in reducing carbon emissions
Steps	Identify costs associated with various carbon reduction interventions, measure and compare costs with effectiveness in reducing CO ₂ emissions, , calculate cost per unit of outcome for each intervention
Best Practices	Use common metric to measure outcomes, account for uncertainty through sensitivity analyses, use country-specific discount rates to account for the time value of money
Threshold for Cost-Effectiveness	Based on local context, such as the country's gross domestic product per capita
Outcome	Identify the most efficient carbon reduction interventions for healthcare facilities and generate valuable information to inform policy decisions

6 Quality Assurance

Quality assurance is crucial in the carbon measurement study to optimize accurate and trustworthy results and reduce bias [48]. The research team will undergo thorough virtual training from the ADKN and experts from CeSHHAR and WITS RHI to master carbon footprint measurement. The virtual training will cover all aspects of the measurement process, including data collection, analysis, and reporting, and stress the significance of adhering to protocols and guidelines. The team will be equipped with the necessary skills and knowledge to deliver high-quality results.

Additionally, the ADKN Carbon Management tool has an error-checking sheet that detects and highlights common errors or inconsistencies in data entry. The sheet provides instructions for fixing these errors, ensuring the integrity of the collected data, and reducing the potential for inaccurate results. Furthermore, the research team will apply data validation techniques, including range checks, format checks, and cross-referencing with external sources, to verify the accuracy and completeness of the data. A detailed record of all activities involved in the

measurement process, including data collection, analysis, and reporting, will be maintained in a logbook throughout the project for traceability and accountability purposes.

7 Ethics and dissemination

Successfully implementing public health programs and policies requires rigorous research to guide decision-making and measure their impact [49]. Such research must be conducted with ethical considerations in mind to ensure that it is responsible, safe, and respectful of the rights and well-being of all involved [50]. This section outlines the ethics and dissemination plan for research on carbon emissions in Kenyan, South African, and Zimbabwean healthcare facilities. We discuss the necessary approvals and certifications, the expertise and skills of the research team, and the measures taken to minimize risks. Finally, we address the public disclosure of information and the dissemination plan to ensure the research findings are accessible to all stakeholders.

7.1 Research ethics approval

Obtaining approvals and certifications in each participating country is necessary to ensure a responsible and ethical approach.

- In Kenya, the team has obtained regulatory approvals from hospital management, and will not require to apply for research ethics approval. The team which contributed to the development of the AKDN tool have already started measuring the carbon emissions at facilities in Kenya. The team will also follow the guidelines outlined in the Aga Khan University Hospital Research Ethics Policy.
- In South Africa, the study team will adhere to nationally relevant legislation such as the South African National Health Act, which sets standards for the

provision of healthcare services in the country, as well as the South African Guidelines for Good Clinical Practice [51, 52]. The team will seek ethics approval from the Wits RHI Research Review Committee and the University of the Witwatersrand Human Research and Ethics Committee, performed within the faculty of Health Sciences at the University of the Witwatersrand. We will also seek approval from the district to proceed with the study. Additionally, all researchers will be trained on good clinical practice and will ensure that all data is collected and stored confidentially.

- In Zimbabwe, the study team will seek regulatory approval to carry out the measurements from the office of the permanent secretary of the Ministry of Health and Child Care. Additionally, the team will seek approval from the custodians of the Mashonaland Central Province who is the Minister of Provincial and Devolution Affairs under the office of the President of Zimbabwe. Only after these approvals are granted will the team be able to collect the measurements. The team will ensure that all data is collected and stored securely.
- The team comprises of highly trained and experienced researchers with expertise in various relevant fields, including public health, epidemiology, environmental science, health economics and data management. The team has extensive experience conducting research in low-resource settings. They have undergone training in research ethics and will adhere to the principles of research ethics throughout the study.
- All three countries have relevant national legislation and guidelines, such as the Kenyan Health Act [54], the South African National Health Act [52], and the Zimbabwe Public Health Act [55], that the team will adhere to throughout the study.
- The research project involves collecting data on carbon emissions and not human participants. However, some risks may be associated with data

collection and management, including confidentiality breaches, unauthorized access, or loss of data. To minimize these risks, the team will ensure that data collection is done securely by implementing password-protected access to data and using encrypted data storage devices. The team will also ensure that any data shared between team members is done securely and kept confidential using SharePoint and password protects email. Additionally, the team will have protocols to handle any adverse events, such as data breaches, and will work with the appropriate authorities to minimize any potential negative impacts. By taking these measures, the team will ensure that the risks associated with the research project are minimized and conducted ethically and responsibly [56].

- Informed consent is a cornerstone of ethical research. It is generally required to ensure that individuals fully understand the purpose and risks of a research project and can voluntarily decide whether or not to participate [57]. However, in this project, the carbon measurements do not involve human participants, and the data will be collected from equipment and facilities. As a result, informed consent is not required. Nonetheless, the research team will take steps to ensure that the data is collected responsibly and ethically and that any potential risks or ethical considerations that emerge are carefully considered and addressed.
- The potential benefits of this research project are significant and extend beyond the participating communities to society as a whole [58]. The project's outcomes will be useful in informing policy development, identifying environmental and health risks, and developing strategies to mitigate those risks. The project's potential to reduce carbon emissions is also significant, as carbon emissions contribute to climate change and negatively impact the environment [59]. Therefore, the benefits of the project, which include better health policy, improved environmental health,

and reduced carbon emissions, far outweigh the potential risks involved.

- Protecting data privacy is critical to ensuring the ethical and responsible conduct of research. We are aware of the data privacy laws in each of the participating countries, including the Kenyan Data Protection Act [60], the South African Protection of Personal Information Act [61], and the Zimbabwe Data Protection Act [62]. We will ensure that all data collected and processed is done so in accordance with these laws and regulations. Our research strategy aligns with these data privacy laws, as we will prioritize data confidentiality, security, and protection.

7.2 Dissemination

We aim to share our findings with local, regional, and global governments, mentioned hereafter, and local stakeholders who can influence policy. The objective is to increase understanding of the implications of our work, and national policies and identify potential remaining knowledge gaps and actions for future work. We intend to share the findings with country-specific groups discussed subsequently.

❖ Kenya, South Africa and Zimbabwe

In all three countries, we plan to present our results at stakeholder meetings, and may include representatives from Health, Environment, Forestry, Fisheries, individuals involved in developing the National Climate plans, professional health worker associations, facility managers, church leaders and community leaders. Additionally, each team will present findings to community advisory boards to engage with the local community and gather their perspectives.

Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication plan. HIGH Horizons has developed a Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) plan, one of the prerequisites of Horizon Europe funding and a deliverable. The DEC plan

serves as a roadmap for the HIGH Horizons consortium partners to guide and keep track of the dissemination and communication activities of all partners and to provide insight to the outcomes and knowledge that will be gained through the project's lifetime. Planned dissemination activities include scientific conferences and publications.

Scientific conferences. Presenting findings at scientific conferences is an important aspect of our project. This provides a platform to share our results with a broader audience of experts, researchers, and decision-makers in climate change, health, and sustainability. We aim to engage with a diverse group of individuals and institutions who may be able to use our findings to inform their work, policies, and decision-making [63].

The conferences we plan to attend will be local and international, providing opportunities to share our findings with a broader audience and receive feedback from experts from different regions and perspectives. The presentations will be structured to effectively communicate our results, including the methods used, main findings, and their implications for policy and practice. This will help promote the use of evidence-based practices and contribute to advancing knowledge in the field.

Participating in scientific conferences will allow us to contribute to the scientific community, establish new collaborations and partnerships, and provide opportunities to learn from others working in the field.

Publications. Publishing the findings of our project in Open Access journals is a vital aspect of disseminating the results to a broader audience. Open Access journals provide a platform for the results to be widely available and easily accessible to a diverse group of individuals, including policymakers, practitioners, researchers, and the general public. This will help promote the use of evidence-based practices and contribute to advancing knowledge in the field.

The manuscripts we plan to publish will provide a comprehensive overview of the study's methods, results and implications. We aim to publish in high-impact, peer-reviewed journals that are widely read and recognized in the relevant fields. This will ensure the results are high quality and receive the necessary recognition and visibility [64].

In addition to publishing the results, we plan to publish the study's methodologies and protocols. This will help others to understand the methods used and to replicate the study if needed. Overall, publishing the results of our project in open-access journals will help promote transparency and accountability, and contribute to advancing knowledge and evidence-based practices in the field [65].

7.3 Strengths

This study has several strengths that increase the validity and generalizability of its findings:

1. *Multi-country approach:* The study covers healthcare facilities in three different sub-Saharan African countries, increasing the diversity of its findings and allowing for cross-country comparisons.
2. *Use of AKDN Carbon Management Tool:* The study will use the AKDN Carbon Management Tool, which has been widely validated and used in previous studies, ensuring the reliability of the data collected.
3. *Longitudinal study design:* The study will use a serial measurements approach, which will enable the tracking of progress over time, providing valuable insights for future sustainability efforts.
4. *Partnership with local health departments:* The study is working closely with local health departments in each country, which will facilitate access to data and ensure the feasibility of implementing mitigation strategies.
5. *Clear communication and dissemination strategy:* The HIGH Horizons project has a well-planned Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication

strategy and plan for disseminating and communicating its findings to relevant stakeholders, including policymakers, researchers, and healthcare professionals, ensuring that the results are widely shared and can inform future efforts.

These strengths will increase the study's impact and contribute to its overall success in improving our understanding of the healthcare sector's contribution to greenhouse gas emissions in sub-Saharan Africa and identifying effective mitigation strategies.

7.4 Limitations

Despite the strengths of this study, there are several limitations that must be acknowledged:

1. *Limited sample size:* The study is limited to eight healthcare facilities in three sub-Saharan African countries, which may not be representative of all healthcare facilities in the region. Therefore, the findings may not be generalizable to other healthcare facilities in the region or other parts of the world.
2. *Incomplete data:* Some facilities may not have accurate or complete data on energy consumption and waste management practices, which could impact the accuracy of the carbon footprint measurements.
3. *Limited timeline:* The study is limited to a three-year timeline, which may not be sufficient to capture all changes in greenhouse gas emissions resulting from mitigation strategies. Longer-term studies would be necessary to fully evaluate the impact of interventions on reducing emissions and achieving sustainability goals.
4. *Resource limitations:* The success of the study depends on the availability of resources and the cooperation of the healthcare facilities. Some facilities

may not have the resources or capacity to implement mitigation strategies, which could impact the effectiveness of the interventions.

5. *External factors*: The study may be limited by external factors that could impact the healthcare facilities' emissions, such as changes in energy prices or natural disasters. These factors are beyond the control of the research team and could impact the accuracy and generalizability of the findings.

Overall, while this study has the potential to provide valuable insights into the carbon footprint of healthcare facilities in sub-Saharan Africa and the effectiveness of mitigation strategies, it is important to acknowledge these limitations and interpret the findings in the context of these limitations.

8 References

1. Seneviratne, S., et al., *Changes in climate extremes and their impacts on the natural physical environment*. 2012.
2. Ebi, K.L., et al., *Extreme Weather and Climate Change: Population Health and Health System Implications*. *Annu Rev Public Health*, 2021. **42**: p. 293-315.
3. Roos, N., et al., *Maternal and newborn health risks of climate change: A call for awareness and global action*. *Acta obstetricia et gynecologica Scandinavica*, 2021. **100**(4): p. 566-570.
4. Kuehn, L. and S. McCormick, *Heat Exposure and Maternal Health in the Face of Climate Change*. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*, 2017. **14**(8).
5. Myers, S.S. and A. Bernstein, *The coming health crisis: indirect health effects of global climate change*. *F1000 Biol Rep*, 2011. **3**: p. 3.
6. Borg, F.H., et al., *Climate change and health in urban informal settlements in low- and middle-income countries - a scoping review of health impacts and adaptation strategies*. *Glob Health Action*, 2021. **14**(1): p. 1908064.
7. Aga Khan Development Network. *Guide to the Aga Khan Development Network's carbon management tool*. 2018.
https://d1zah1nkiby91r.cloudfront.net/s3fs-public/guide_to_the_aga_khan_development_networks_carbon_management_tool.pdf.
8. Baddley, J. *Guide to the Aga Khan Development Network's Carbon Management Tool* 2022.

9. King, P.T., et al., Co-design for indigenous and other children and young people from priority social groups: A systematic review. *SSM-Population Health*, 2022: p. 101077.
10. Weatherspark. (n.d.). Average Weather in Mombasa, Kenya Year Round. Retrieved from <https://weatherspark.com/y/101135/Average-Weather-in-Mombasa-KenyaRound>.
11. Fares, A., Factors influencing the seasonal patterns of infectious diseases. *Int J Prev Med*, 2013. **4**(2): p. 128-32.
12. Garland, R., et al., CITY OF TSHWANE CLIMATE RISK & VULNERABILITY ASSESSMENT. 2015.
13. Li, X., L.C. Stringer, and M. Dallimer, The Impacts of Urbanisation and Climate Change on the Urban Thermal Environment in Africa. *Climate*, 2022. **10**(11): p. 164.
14. The Trans-African Hydro-Meteorological Observatory (TAHMO). TAHMO weather data.
15. The World Bank. World Development Indicators: Data for Upper middle income, South Africa 2021.
16. Mabuza, L.H., et al., Awareness of health care practitioners about the national health insurance in tshwane district, south africa. *The Open Public Health Journal*, 2018. **11**(1).
17. Statistics South Africa. (2021). Mid-year population estimates 2021. Retrieved from <https://www.statssa.gov.za/publications/P0302/P03022021.pdf>.
18. City of Tshwane Metropolitan Municipality. (n.d.). City of Tshwane Official Website. Retrieved from https://www.tshwane.gov.za/?page_id=10032.
19. Ilunga, B.B., et al., Interpreting Mamelodi Community-Oriented Primary Care data on tuberculosis loss to follow-up through the lens of intersectionality. *Afr J Prim Health Care Fam Med*, 2020. **12**(1): p. e1-e6.
20. Ncube, A. and M. Tawodzera, Communities' perceptions of health hazards induced by climate change in Mount Darwin district, Zimbabwe. *Jambá Journal of Disaster Risk Studies*, 2019. **11**.
21. tcktcktck. (n.d.). Mount Darwin, Mashonaland Central, Zimbabwe. Retrieved from <https://tcktcktck.org/zimbabwe/mashonaland-central/mount-darwin>.
22. Climate-Data.org. (n.d.). Climate: Mount Darwin - Climate graph, Temperature graph, Climate table. Retrieved from <https://en.climate-data.org/africa/zimbabwe/mashonaland-central-1610/>.
23. The World Bank. World Development Indicators: Data for Lower middle income, Zimbabwe 2021.
24. 2022_population_and_housing_census_preliminary_report_on_population_figures.pdf.
25. Zimbabwe National Statistics Agency and Unicef. Zimbabwe Multiple Indicator Cluster Survey 2019, Survey Findings Report. In: ZIMSTAT and UNICEF Harare, Zimbabwe; 2019.

26. *The Committee on Morbidity and Mortality in Children Under 5 Years (CoMMiC). 4th Triennial Report of The Committee on Morbidity and Mortality In Children Under 5 Years (CoMMiC): 2017 - 2020; 2020.*
27. *Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. (n.d.). Heat Stress: Protecting Workers from the Effects of Heat. Retrieved from <https://www.cdc.gov/niosh/topics/repro/heat.html#:~:text=Take%20steps%20to%20prevent%20heat,not%20provide%20adequate%20cooling%20breaks>.*
28. *Samaritan's Purse. (n.d.). Karanda Mission Hospital, Mt. Darwin, Zimbabwe. Retrieved from <https://www.samaritanspurse.org/medical/karanda-mission-hospital-mt-darwin-zimbabwe/>.*
29. *Ministry of Health and Child Care (MoHCC). (n.d.). Zimbabwe Health Information System (HIS).*
30. *Doctor4Africa. (n.d.). Dotito Rural Health Clinic. Retrieved from <https://doctor4africa.com/listing/zimbabwe/hospital,rural-health-clinic/dotito-rural-health-clinic/>.*
31. *Samaritan's Purse. (n.d.). Karanda Mission Hospital, Mt. Darwin, Zimbabwe. Retrieved from <https://www.samaritanspurse.org/medical/karanda-mission-hospital-mt-darwin-zimbabwe/>.*
32. *Brown, L.H., P.G. Buettner, and D.V. Canyon, The energy burden and environmental impact of health services. Am J Public Health, 2012. **102**(12): p. e76-82.*
33. *Reddy, K.P., et al., Cost-effectiveness of public health strategies for COVID-19 epidemic control in South Africa: a microsimulation modelling study. Lancet Glob Health, 2021. **9**(2): p. e120-e129.*
34. *Greene, L.A., EHPnet: United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. 2000.*
35. *Gray, A.M., et al., Applied methods of cost-effectiveness analysis in healthcare. Vol. 3. 2010: OUP Oxford.*
36. *Optima. (n.d.). Optima: Modelling to improve health. Retrieved from <http://optimamodel.com/>.*
37. *Marshall, D.A., et al., Addressing challenges of economic evaluation in precision medicine using dynamic simulation modeling. Value in health, 2020. **23**(5): p. 566-573.*
38. *World Health Organization. (2023). Health financing. WHO Health Topics. Retrieved from https://www.who.int/health-topics/health-financing#tab=tab_1.*
39. *Horton, T.J., J.H. Illingworth, and W.H. Warburton, Overcoming challenges in codifying and replicating complex health care interventions. Health Affairs, 2018. **37**(2): p. 191-197.*
40. *Gray, A.M., et al., Applied methods of cost-effectiveness analysis in healthcare. Vol. 3. 2010: OUP Oxford.*
41. *ProjectManager.com. (n.d.). Quick guide to resource management. Retrieved from <https://www.projectmanager.com/blog/quick-guide-resource-management>.*

42. Lock, R.H., et al., *Statistics: Unlocking the power of data*. 2020: John Wiley & Sons.
43. Midway, S.R., *Principles of effective data visualization*. *Patterns*, 2020. **1**(9): p. 100141.
44. Tennison, I., et al., *Health care's response to climate change: a carbon footprint assessment of the NHS in England*. *The Lancet Planetary Health*, 2021. **5**(2): p. e84-e92.
45. Russell, L.B., et al., *The role of cost-effectiveness analysis in health and medicine*. *Jama*, 1996. **276**(14): p. 1172-1177.
46. Williams, M.L., et al., *The Lancet Countdown on health benefits from the UK Climate Change Act: a modelling study for Great Britain*. *The Lancet Planetary Health*, 2018. **2**(5): p. e202-e213.
47. MacNeill, A.J., F. McGain, and J.D. Sherman, *Planetary health care: a framework for sustainable health systems*. *The Lancet Planetary Health*, 2021. **5**(2): p. e66-e68.
48. Montgomery, D.C., *Introduction to statistical quality control*. 2020: John Wiley & Sons.
49. Brown, A.F., et al., *Structural interventions to reduce and eliminate health disparities*. *American journal of public health*, 2019. **109**(S1): p. S72-S78.
50. Kruger, M., P. Ndebele, and L. Horn, *Research ethics in Africa: A resource for research ethics committees*. 2014: African Sun Media.
51. South African Health Products Regulatory Authority (SAHPRA). (2020). *South African Good Clinical Practice Guidelines*. Retrieved from https://www.sahpra.org.za/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/SA-GCP-2020_Final.pdf.
52. University of Pretoria. (2013). *National Health Act, No. 61 of 2003*. Retrieved from https://www.up.ac.za/media/shared/12/ZP_Files/health-act.zp122778.pdf.
53. Medical Research Council of Zimbabwe (MRCZ). (2011). *Ethics Guidelines for Health Research Involving Human Participants in Zimbabwe 2011*. Retrieved from <http://www.mrcz.org.zw/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/Ethics-Guidelines-for-Health-Research-Involving-Human-Participants-in-Zimbabwe-2011.pdf>.
54. Government of Kenya. (2012). *Public Health Act, Cap 242*. Retrieved from <http://kenyalaw.org/kl/fileadmin/pdfdownloads/Acts/PublicHealthActCap242.pdf>.
55. Government of Zimbabwe. (2018). *Public Health Act [Chapter 15:09]*. Retrieved from <https://faolex.fao.org/docs/pdf/zim190656.pdf>.
56. Goldsteen, A., et al., *Data minimization for GDPR compliance in machine learning models*. *AI and Ethics*, 2021: p. 1-15.
57. Kadam, R.A., *Informed consent process: a step further towards making it meaningful! Perspectives in clinical research*, 2017. **8**(3): p. 107.
58. National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences (NIEHS). (n.d.). *What is Bioethics?* Retrieved from <https://www.niehs.nih.gov/research/resources/bioethics/whatis/index.cfm>.

59. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. (n.d.). *Climate Effects on Health*. Retrieved from <https://www.cdc.gov/climateandhealth/effects/default.htm#:~:text=The%20health%20effects%20of%20these,and%20threats%20to%20mental%20health>.
60. Office of the Data Protection Commissioner (ODPC). (2019). *Data Protection Act*. Retrieved from <https://www.odpc.go.ke/dpa-act/>.
61. South African Government. (2013). *Protection of Personal Information Act, 2013*. Retrieved from <https://www.gov.za/documents/protection-personal-information-act>.
62. Government of Zimbabwe. (2019). *Data Protection Act [Chapter 24:27]*. Retrieved from https://www.veritaszim.net/sites/veritas_d/files/DataProtectionAct_1.pdf.
63. National Institutes of Health. (2021). *Data Management and Sharing Policy*. Retrieved from <https://sharing.nih.gov/data-management-and-sharing-policy>.
64. Triaridis, S. and A. Kyrgidis, *Peer review and journal impact factor: the two pillars of contemporary medical publishing*. *Hippokratia*, 2010. **14**(Suppl 1): p. 5-12.
65. Springer Nature. (n.d.). *Open Research - Benefits*. Retrieved from <https://www.springernature.com/gp/open-research/about/benefits>.
66. Vassall, A., Sweeney, S., Kahn, J., Gomez Guillen, G., Bollinger, L., Marseille, E., Herzel, B., DeCormier Plosky, W., Cunnama, L., Sinanovic, E. and Bautista-Arredondo, S., 2017. *Reference case for estimating the costs of global health services and interventions*.
67. Atomica — Atomica documentation [Internet]. [cited 2023 Apr 24]. Available from: <https://atomica.tools/docs/master/index.html>

9 Annexure A

Note: It's worth noting that Kenya has been conducting the AKDN Carbon Management Tool for a number of years, and therefore, may have already implemented some mitigation interventions. As a result, the timelines for implementing interventions in Kenya, Zimbabwe, and South Africa may differ based on their current status and the unique needs and circumstances of each location.

9.1 Kenya schedule of activities

Project Month (2022-2026)	Oct-22	Nov-22	Dec-22	Jan-23	Feb-23	Mar-23	Apr-23	May-23	Jun-23	Jul-23	Aug-23	Sep-23	Oct-23	Nov-23	Dec-23	2024	2025	2026
Measurement of carbon footprints at three health facilities	Starting Oct 2022 to end evaluation (~ 2 years)																	
Design and optimization of mitigation interventions				X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X							
Tool for modelling alternative mitigation interventions				X	X	X												
Implementation of mitigation interventions in health facilities							Starting April 2023 to Dec 2023	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		
Evaluation of effectiveness and cost-effectiveness	Starting October 2022 to July 2026										X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
Dissemination of findings					Starting Feb 2023 to Aug 2026	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

9.2 South Africa schedule of activities

Project Month (2022-2026)	Oct-22	Nov-22	Dec-22	Jan-23	Feb-23	Mar-23	Apr-23	May-23	Jun-23	Jul-23	Aug-23	Sep-23	Oct-23	Nov-23	Dec-23	2024	2025	2026
Consultation/ Planning	X	X	X	X														
Ethics submission (RRC& HREC)					X	X												
Measurement of carbon footprints at three health facilities						Starting March 2023 to end evaluation (-2 years)												
Design and optimization of mitigation interventions								X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			
Tool for modelling alternative mitigation interventions								X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		
Implementation of mitigation interventions in health facilities										Starting July 2023 to December 2023	X	X	X	X	X	X		
Evaluation of effectiveness and cost-effectiveness	Starting October 2022 to July 2026										X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
Dissemination of findings					Starting Feb 2023 to Aug 2026	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

9.3 Zimbabwe schedule of activities

Project Month (2022-2026)	Oct 2022	Nov 2022	Dec 2022	Jan 2023	Feb 2023	Mar 2023	Apr 2023	May 2023	Jun 2023	Jul 2023	Aug 2023	Sept 2023	Oct 2023	Nov 2023	2024	2025	2026
Support letter application to the Ministry of Health and Child Care		X															
Memorandum of Understanding application from Mashonaland Central Provincial Affairs and Devolution Minister			X	X													
Measurement of carbon footprints at proposed health facilities						Starting March 2023 to end evaluation (~2 years)											
Design and optimization of mitigation interventions				X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		
Tool for modelling alternative mitigation interventions						X	X	X	X	X	X	X			X	X	
Implementation of mitigation interventions in health facilities												Starting Sept 2023 to Feb 2024			X	X	X
Evaluation of effectiveness and cost-effectiveness	Starting Oct 2022 to July 2026																
Dissemination of findings					Starting Feb 2023 to Aug 2026												